

Size	Neon (LUPS)	Taichi (LUPS)	Speedup
4096×1024	33346.73	29304.42	1.14
8192×2048	33740.24	33979.88	0.99
16384×4096	34001.84	34729.78	0.98
32768×8192	206079.33	206127	0.999

Neon’s speedup over Taichi [11] on the 2D Kármán Vortex Street LBM application using LUPS metric. Experiments were run on a single GPU of a DGX A100 server.

Percentage of the halo update process that is overlapped with computation on the Poisson solver using the different OCC options offered by Neon. The percentage is computed as $T_{overlap}/T_{com}$, where T_{com} is the time between the beginning of the first memory transfer of the halo update process and the end of the last transfer and $T_{overlap}$ is the part of T_{com} that is overlapped with computation. Note that the No OCC option has 0% of overlap, and therefore it was not included in the plot. The data was collected by profiling the Poisson solver on 6 GV100 GPUs and with a domain of size 320^3 . Measurements were averaged over a number of 10 iterations.